

“EXPERIENCE OF TREATING NECROTIZING FASCIITIS, ORGANISMS INVOLVED AND LIMB SALVAGEABILITY: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY”

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess the experience of treating patients with “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” at a tertiary care institute in terms of limb salvageability and organisms involved.

Study Design: Prospective Cross-Sectional Study.

Place and Duration of Study: Department of General Surgery, PEMH, Rawalpindi, from September 2023 to February 2024.

Patients & Methods: A total of 94 patients diagnosed with “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” of the extremities were included. Surgical data were analyzed to identify the organisms causing NF and the limb outcomes. Data analysis was performed using SPSS 22.0.

Results: The mean age was 45.56 ± 6.54 years. There were 56 (57.14%) males and 42 (42.86%) females. Thirty-four (34.69%) patients were diabetic, and 50 (51.02%) were smokers. The most common organism isolated was Group A Streptococcus in 44 (44.90%) patients. Limb salvage was achieved in 74 (75.51%) patients, while 24 (24.49%) required amputation.

Conclusion: In this prospective study, the most common causative organism of “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” was Group A Streptococcus, and the incidence of limb salvage was 75.51%.

INTRODUCTION

“Necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” is a condition characterized by severe and life-threatening infection of the soft tissues of the body and skin, which can lead to necrosis of the “muscular fascia”

and “subcutaneous tissues”.¹ The “fascial plane”, through which this disease typically disseminates, exhibits a significantly compromised circulation of blood. Consequently, tissues nearby at the first

stage of infection remain unaffected, which can cause a delay in both the early detection and treatment of this severely debilitating condition resulting in rapid spreading to the fascia, skin, underlying soft tissue and muscles.² Diagnosing necrotizing infections of the soft tissue is challenging due to their rarity, with approximate incidence of 1.1-1.4 cases every hundred thousand people and a mortality rate exceeding to as high as 29%.³ Given the fast spread and potential for mimicry with less severe ailments, a timely and precise diagnosis is of utmost importance.⁴

“Gram-positive cocci”, in particular “Staphylococcus aureus” and “Streptococci”, are the main causes of this condition.⁵ Furthermore, the occurrence of multi-microbial infestations might arise due to the simultaneous infection by “anaerobic” and “gram-negative” microorganisms.⁵ During its clinical progression, the skin first exhibits no visible alterations, subsequently transitioning from a “red” to “purplish-red” and eventually “grayish-blue” coloration over days. In addition, skin undergoes a process of hardening and swelling, resulting in a glossy appearance and a warm sensation when touched.⁶ The epidermis becomes highly sensitive to touch and may elicit a greater degree of pain than the actual physical damage it appears to be producing.⁶ Within a span of few days, the skin undergoes disintegration, leading to the creation of bullae and the development of gangrene in the affected area.⁶ Systemic manifestations such as elevated body temperature, accelerated heart rate and systemic toxicity are indicative of NF associated sepsis and subsequent septic shock which augments the chances of mortality.⁷ An additional factor that is strongly associated with this rapidly progressive and life-threatening infection is the potential to suffer from life-long disability secondary to loss of the limb.⁸

Owing to such strong association with high degree of function impairing morbidity and mortality, it is essential to audit the performance of healthcare centers regarding their practices to manage the patients with “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)”. This can help improve not only in updating and mapping the microbiological spectrum of this infectious disease but also the overall patient outcome.

Therefore, this study was conducted with the aim of determining the prevalence of organisms causing “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” and incidence of limb salvageability.

METHODOLOGY

This Prospective cross sectional study was conducted at surgical department of “PEMH, Rawalpindi from September 2023 to February 2024”. Appropriate sample size was calculated using “WHO sample size calculator for population proportion with specified absolute precision” using following formula⁹:

For calculations, following assumptions were used; “confidence interval of 95%”, “absolute precision of 8%” and “anticipated incidence of limb salvage in patients with necrotizing fasciitis” of 79.6%.¹⁰ This gave a sample size of 98.

$$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

Inclusion criteria: Patients were over the age of 18 years, both males and females who were admitted with “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” of the extremity in which culture of necrotic tissue/purulent discharge was obtained were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who had evidence of infection at other part of body (like neck, trunk or head), had bilateral disease, had received antibiotics previously within last 2 weeks, had a recent debridement of a wound on extremities in last 2 weeks, those who did not had tissue/discharge culture and those who were younger than eighteen years were excluded from the study.

Patients were enrolled through a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. The diagnosis of necrotizing fasciitis (NF) was established using a combination of clinical scoring and surgico-pathological evaluation. Clinically, the Laboratory Risk Indicator for Necrotizing Fasciitis (LRINEC) score was applied, and a score of ≥ 6.5 was considered diagnostic for NF. Surgico-pathological confirmation was based on operative evidence of purulent discharge from necrotic tissue along with histopathological findings such as polymorphonuclear infiltrates, vasculitis, necrosis,

and thrombosis. All surgical procedures were performed by consultant surgeons with a minimum of five years of experience, while pathological assessments were carried out by consultant pathologists with at least two years of experience.

Following enrollment, baseline characteristics—including age, gender, diabetes status, smoking status, involved limb, and side of involvement—were prospectively recorded. The type of wound dressing used (normal saline, povidone-iodine, or vacuum dressing) was documented for each patient. Culture reports obtained during the course of management were reviewed, and the isolated organisms were noted. Limb outcomes, classified as either salvaged or amputated, were also recorded. Patients with deeper necrosis extending into muscle or with rapidly advancing infection underwent limb amputation, whereas the remaining patients received serial debridement along with antibiotic therapy.

Data analysis was carried out using SPSS version 20. Normality was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Quantitative variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation or median (IQR), and

qualitative variables as frequencies and percentages. Limb outcomes were compared across different dressing types using the Chi-square test, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this prospective study, 98 patients were enrolled. The mean age of the participants was 45.56 ± 6.54 years. Among them, 56 (57.14%) were male and 42 (42.86%) were female. A total of 34 (34.69%) patients were diabetics, whereas 64 (65.31%) were non-diabetics. There were 50 (51.02%) smokers and 48 (48.98%) non-smokers. Upper limb NF was identified in 49 (50.00%) patients, while the remaining 49 (50.00%) had lower limb involvement. The left limb was affected in 50 (51.02%) patients, and the right limb in 48 (48.98%) patients. The most frequently applied dressing during the study period was povidone-iodine in 48 (48.97%) cases, followed by vacuum dressing in 26 (26.53%) and normal saline dressing in 24 (24.50%). These clinico-demographic characteristics of the participants are summarized below in Table I.

Table I: Clinico-demographic characteristics (n = 98)

Sr. No.	Characteristics	n (%)
1	Mean age	45.56 ± 6.54 years
2	Gender Male Female	56 (57.14%) 42 (42.86%)
3	Diabetes Yes No	34 (34.69%) 64 (65.31%).
4	Smoking Yes No	50 (51.02%) 48 (48.98%)
5	Limb involved Upper limb Lower limb	49 (50.00%) 49 (50.00%)
6	Side of limb involved Left Right	50 (51.02%) 48 (48.98%)

7	Type of dressing used Normal saline dressing Povidone iodine dressing Vacuum dressing	24 (24.50%) 48 (48.97%) 26 (26.53%)
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Among the organisms isolated on tissue or discharge culture in this prospective study, the most frequently identified pathogen was Group A Streptococcus in 44 (44.90%) patients, followed by Staphylococcus aureus in 24 (24.50%).

Polymicrobial growth was observed in 12 (12.24%) patients, while Pseudomonas and Escherichia coli were each isolated in 9 (9.18%) patients. These findings are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Microbiological spectrum of “Necrotizing Fasciitis (NF)” (n = 98)

Incidence of limb salvage in patients with “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” was 74 (75.51%) while

24 (24.49%) patients had their limb amputated. This is depicted below in figure 2:

Figure 2: Incidence of limb salvage & amputation (n = 98)

Comparison of limb outcome by type of dressing used is given below in table II:

Table II: Comparison of limb outcome by type of dressing (n = 98)

Type of dressing	Limb Salvaged (n = 74)	Limb amputated (n = 24)	p-value
Normal saline dressing	18 (24.32%)	6 (25.00%)	0.981
Povidone-iodine dressing	36 (48.65%)	12 (50.00%)	
Vacuum dressing	20 (27.03%)	6 (25.00%)	

DISCUSSION

Necrotizing fasciitis (NF) is a highly hazardous health problem that presents significant challenges for surgeons and healthcare professionals. It is characterized by a rapidly advancing, invasive, and progressive infection that can spread aggressively within hours and may even lead to multiple organ dysfunction.^{13,14} In a prospective context, the evaluation and treatment difficulties of “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” arise from the fact that its clinical signs and symptoms resemble those of many other infections, making accurate assessment difficult for physicians.^{15,16} This has contributed to an increased rate of poor outcomes in extremity “necrotizing fasciitis (NF),” particularly in the form of limb loss.¹⁷ This prospective study therefore focused on the treatment experience of “necrotizing fasciitis (NF),” with particular emphasis on identifying the organisms involved and the incidence of limb salvage.

In this study, more than half of the patients suffering from “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” were males, which is consistent with findings from a study reporting that the condition is more common in men.¹⁸ Diabetes and smoking were present in a considerable proportion of patients, aligning with the fact that both smoking and diabetes suppress the immune system.^{19,20} and may therefore play a role in increasing susceptibility to this severe infection. Group A Streptococcus was identified as a major contributor to the development of “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” in the present study, consistent with previous literature describing this organism as a leading cause of NF.²¹ Limb salvage was achieved in more than three-quarters of the study population, while one-quarter of the patients underwent amputation. This was lower than the

incidence reported by Park et al.¹⁰ who documented an amputation rate of nearly 80%. Another study reported that one-third of affected limbs were amputated,²² which was higher than in the present study. An additional aspect evaluated in this prospective analysis was the effect of the type of wound dressing used after initial debridement on limb outcome. It was found that there was no statistically significant difference between dressing types and the rates of limb salvage or amputation, consistent with a meta-analysis reporting that although dressing type significantly reduced mortality in NF patients, it had no impact on complication rates.²³

This study shows that, in the present institutional setting, the overall experience and outcomes for patients suffering from “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” were favorable. This audit will help identify shortcomings in the treatment protocols for this condition. It is recommended that similar audits be conducted in all institutions managing NF so that limb outcomes can be optimized on a larger scale. A major limitation of this study was its reliance on previous data, which restricted the sample size. Therefore, it is recommended that future work be conducted prospectively as a long-term cohort study to allow a more comprehensive assessment.

CONCLUSION

This prospective study found that the most common organism isolated as a cause of “necrotizing fasciitis (NF)” was Group A Streptococcus, and the incidence of limb salvage was 75.51%.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

“We declare that there was no conflict of interest”.

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